

Island Resilience is American Resilience: Actions Towards Reducing the Impacts of Invasive Species on US and US Affiliated Islands

INVASIVE SPECIES ADVISORY COMMITTEE¹
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Introduction

ISLANDS MATTER FOR U.S. FOOD PRODUCTION, ECONOMIES, BIODIVERSITY, CULTURAL HERITAGE, AND NATIONAL SECURITY

Second only to the impacts of climate change, invasive species severely damage food security, economies, ecosystems, and cultures on islands worldwide (Brewington et al., 2023; Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services [IPBES], 2023; Micronesian Islands Forum [MIF], 2024a, 2024b). Invasive species are responsible for almost 90% of recorded species extinctions on islands and billions of dollars in damages (Bellard et al., 2016; IPBES, 2023). An economic analysis found that invasive species have cost U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands² more than \$16 billion in cumulative damages to agriculture, public health, ecosystems, and infrastructure between 1989 to 2019 (Brewington, unpublished data; Turbelin et al., 2023). When adjusted by land area and population size, these costs to islands are more than seven times greater than those to the continental United States and are more than double the cost per capita. In part, this is because the invasive species burden on many islands is exceptionally high: the State of Hawai‘i, for example, has an almost equal number of non-native plant species as the entire continental United States combined, despite having an area that is less than 0.4% in size (Simpson & Eyler, 2018).

U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands are also home to many underserved and frontline communities that are uniquely vulnerable to the effects of climate change, which has grave implications for the spread, establishment, and management of invasive species (Brewington et al., 2024; Invasive Species Advisory Committee [ISAC], 2023a; Kappes et al., 2021; Lenzner et al., 2020). The issue of invasive species has reached a top level of importance to the U.S.-affiliated Pacific Islands as evidenced by a letter to U.S. President Joe Biden written by the 10 Presidents and Governors of the Micronesian Islands Forum (MIF) in June, 2024. The MIF leaders’ letter stated: “... the long lasting and devastating impacts of invasive species reduce climate change resiliency by altering ecosystem structure and function while also negatively impacting livelihoods, quality of life, food security and culture” (MIF, 2024a, 2024b).

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¹ The composition of the Invasive Species Advisory Committee is listed in the Acknowledgments section. Suggested citation: Invasive Species Advisory Committee. (2024). *Island Resilience is American Resilience: Actions Towards Reducing the Impacts of Invasive Species on US and US Affiliated Islands*. U.S. Department of the Interior, Washington, DC. <https://www.doi.gov/invasivespecies/isac-white-papers>.

² The term “U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands” is used to collectively refer to all U.S. States and Territories that are entirely or partly comprised of oceanic islands in the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans, as well as the Freely Associated States of Palau, the Marshall Islands, and the Federated States of Micronesia (Figure 1).

Islands are ecologically isolated by expanses of ocean, which reduce the numbers and types of plants and animals that are able to colonize their land and the marine environments without the influence of people. Indigenous human communities historically produced all the food and materials needed to sustain island populations, and the ingress of new people, plants, and animals was very low. However, many islands today have much higher populations of residents and visitors and import the vast majority of their food and materials, resulting in an exponential increase in opportunities for new species to be transported to islands.

In the United States, one quarter of all species listed on the Endangered Species Act are from islands, with 646 species evaluated and listed in the State of Hawai'i and the territories of Puerto Rico, Guam, American Sāmoa, the U.S. Virgin Islands (USVI), and the Commonwealth of the Northern Mariana Islands (CNMI) (U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service [USFWS], 2024a). Invasive species are a primary contributor to these species' endangered status and have caused catastrophic losses to native and endemic species in islands, including species extinction and ecosystem collapse (Haines et al., 2024). Many established invaders must also be actively managed in perpetuity, merely one flight or shipment away from continental ports and other island jurisdictions (e.g., the brown treesnake [*Boiga irregularis*] on Guam, the Mediterranean fruit fly [*Ceratitidis capitata*] in Hawai'i).

On many U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands, established or emerging invasive species pose serious risks to continental agricultural industries and human health (e.g. fruit flies, land snails, mosquitos, giant hornets, and cotton pests). Further, the devastating impacts of many invasive species, such as the destabilization of agricultural systems and economies, as well as the loss of ecosystem function and services, have implications for U.S. national security by heightening the risks of future pandemics, conflict, mass migration, political instability, loss of social cohesion, and economic harm (Schoonover et al., 2021). The U.S.-affiliated Pacific Island countries with their enormous Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs)³ are particularly critical with respect to global diplomacy and relations, as well as U.S. defense capabilities, but are also a highly vulnerable corridor for invasive species introductions to other islands and the continent. In recognition of these risks, Federal regulations require the pre-departure or port of entry inspection of all cargo, conveyances, and persons from Hawai'i, Puerto Rico, Guam, the CNMI, and the USVI to the continental United States (Code of Federal Regulations §318.13.8).

Ultimately, islands are a bellwether for invasive species impacts, both nationally and globally, and are indicative

of what continental communities and ecosystems may experience in the future. Accordingly, science, systems, and solutions developed to address invasive species on islands may be widely applicable across the United States and facilitate more proactive response. Because islands are often gateways for emerging invasive species elsewhere (Seebens et al., 2018; U.S. Department of Agriculture [USDA], 2024a), the prevention and management of invasive species on islands should be integrated into policies and actions at all jurisdictional levels to prevent their establishment, address their impacts, and avoid further spread. This paper responds to a request by U.S. Federal agencies and departments for the Invasive Species Advisory Committee (ISAC) to address the unique challenges that invasive species bring to U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands and offers recommendations for transforming how invasive species are considered within planning, processes, policy, and management decisions for islands.

GEOGRAPHIC SCOPE AND STRUCTURE OF THE PAPER

The geographic scope of this paper includes all U.S. States and Territories that are entirely or partly comprised of oceanic islands in the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans, as well as the Freely Associated States of Palau, the Marshall Islands, and the Federated States of Micronesia (Figure 1). These islands reflect a diversity of political statuses, as well as diverse population characteristics, biological resources, historical contexts, and invasive species challenges that are also faced by U.S. continental islands with lower rates of endemism and higher similarity to their adjacent landmasses (e.g., the Channel Islands, the Florida Keys, the Aleutian and Bering Sea Islands). Federal agencies' roles on these islands also vary according to whether they are States, Territories, or in free association with the United States, and the regulatory structure, authorities, and conditions differ.

The paper is focused on four priority action areas that highlight top regulatory, policy, and implementation gaps around U.S. Federal engagement on islands: 1) terrestrial biosecurity⁴, 2) marine biosecurity, 3) control measures and long-term impact reduction, and 4) social and capacity conditions. **These priorities for islands are urgent, feasible, and actionable, and refer to invasive species issues of general importance to the entire United States.** The paper concludes with a set of recommendations that can guide agencies in better meeting the needs of U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands regarding invasive species.

3 An EEZ is an area of the ocean, generally extending 200 nautical miles (230 miles) beyond a nation's territorial sea, within which it has jurisdiction over both living and nonliving resources (United Nations General Assembly, 1982).

4 In this paper, the term "biosecurity" encompasses pre-border, at-the-border, and post-border policies and practices intended to prevent the arrival and establishment of invasive species, including weeds, vertebrate and invertebrate pests, and diseases, and protect the environment and society from their potential negative effects. It is distinct from other concepts such as biosafety, laboratory biosecurity, or bioterrorism.

Figure 1. Map of the U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands that represent the geographic scope of this paper: the State of Hawai'i; the territories of Puerto Rico, Guam, American Sāmoa, the USVI, and the CNMI; and the Freely Associated States of Palau, the Marshall Islands, and the Federated States of Micronesia. The EEZs are shown in blue and make up 3.8 million square miles in area, slightly larger than the land area of the continental United States.

Priority Action Areas

1. TERRESTRIAL BIOSECURITY

In part because of their isolation and unique ecological characteristics, islands are highly susceptible to and disproportionately affected by terrestrial invasive species (Bellard et al., 2016; Seebens et al., 2018; Vitousek et al., 1997). In addition, due to limited human and financial capital, many U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands do not have sufficient capacity, funding, or facilities to rapidly respond to new or emerging biosecurity threats. This section discusses the need for improved prevention efforts and addressing gaps in jurisdictional coordination for more efficient and equitable terrestrial biosecurity on U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands.

1.1 Prevention Efforts

Island communities increasingly require a constant inflow of goods (commodities, cargo, and their conveyances) to sustain residential populations, visitor volume, and economies. This pattern of extensive inbound trade is one of the primary pathways for the introduction of invasive species; therefore, it should be a top priority for implementing effective preventative policies and actions.

Inbound foreign commerce is regulated by Federal agencies to reduce risks to U.S. resources, where each agency prioritizes its actions to reflect its mission, jurisdiction, and international obligations. For the U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA) mission areas (people, agriculture, and natural resources), for instance, this focus results in regulatory decisions that protect the U.S. agricultural resources that hold the greatest domestic economic importance (e.g., commodities like wheat, soy, beef, and tree species used for commercial timber). Therefore, the current process for how risks are identified and deemed actionable by USDA does not always reflect environmental or economic needs on U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands, which decreases the effectiveness of safeguarding actions like prevention and rapid response. Invasive species that threaten smaller scale tropical crops, traditional foods, and/or native non-commercial trees are currently underrepresented on Federal lists. Organisms that are deemed incapable of establishing into continental climates or are unlikely to affect high priority continental species or systems may also readily establish in tropical island ecosystems.

Individual governments of the United States, including Hawai'i, the USVI, and Puerto Rico, do not have the authority to regulate incoming foreign commerce. Meanwhile, Federal

agencies do not enforce State or Territory preventative policies and species exclusion lists unless complex agreements are established. There are, however, some existing programs and models that address the need for State and Territorial priorities to be formally reflected in Federal action at ports of entry:

- States and Territories can petition the USDA Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service (APHIS) to recognize State quarantines excluding individual plant pests at ports of entry through the Federally Recognized State Managed Phytosanitary (FRSMP) program.
- The territory of Guam has unique Memorandums of Understanding (MOUs) between Guam Customs and Quarantine and the Department of Homeland Security (DHS) Customs and Border Protection (CBP), and between the Guam Department of Agriculture-Biosecurity Division and APHIS. These authorize the Guam agencies to search, identify, and determine the disposition of foreign cargo.
- The “Hawai’i Ant Policy,” enacted in 2002, directs that all non-established ant species are Federally actionable/regulated when they are intercepted in foreign cargo or conveyances bound for or in transit through Hawai’i (Hawaii Ant Group, 2007). This was based on a petition and a pest risk analysis that considered the extreme impacts of ant introductions on islands.

Federal, State, and Territorial agencies should work together and share information to advance prevention at ports of entry, but significant barriers prevent effective collaborations and timely information sharing. Data and data management systems for recording and analyzing imported commodities, exporters, importers, and producers from foreign sources into the United States and analysis tools by CBP are proprietary and under security restrictions. The collected information is held back due to the Uniform Trade Secrets Act and DHS restrictions. Under MOUs and joint operations, information may be shared on a controlled and regular basis by CBP to its Federal agency partners such as APHIS, the U.S. Department of Defense (DOD), the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), and the U.S. Department of the Interior (DOI). However, these agencies do not have a similar controlled, timely, and regular conduit of sharing information with their State and Territorial government counterparts. Some Federal agencies disclose findings on a quarterly, monthly, or discretionary (i.e., at the discretion/opinion of a Federal entity) schedule to their State or Territorial counterparts. There is no single platform, user interface, or other mechanism to share real-time data between Federal agencies, or from Federal agencies to States and Territories. This relates to the movement and interception of cargo and conveyances entering the United States bound for U.S.-affiliated islands. One notable exception to this situation is Guam, where the previously mentioned MOUs between CBP, APHIS, and the government of Guam foster timely and regular information sharing and could serve as a model for other Territories.

To address the broad lack of formal avenues for sharing prevention, interception, and situational awareness-related information at ports of entry, some jurisdictions have pest risk committees where Federal and local regulatory agencies discuss invasive species interceptions and other issues that may be of interest. However, these committees, when they do exist, do not represent a consistent solution to information sharing challenges. Even within them, CBP and APHIS do not share interception information in a timely manner with State and Territorial governments, nor do all other relevant Federal agencies (including DOD, NOAA, and the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service [USFWS]) participate regularly.

Cargo and conveyances entering U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands from domestic origins also present a high risk to islands yet are not subject to and do not benefit from the same regulatory, inspection, and risk-mitigation practices as international trade. Agencies with prevention, inspection, and response authorities in Hawai’i and the U.S. Territories have taken on much of this responsibility, and the Freely Associated States already have this sovereign authority, but all lack sufficient capacity to do it thoroughly. This greatly increases the opportunities for invasive species from the continental United States to be introduced into island communities.

U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands have added invasive species risk from two specific pathways: tourism and the U.S. military. These pathways represent high numbers per capita and public audiences that are transient in nature, which makes it difficult to convey invasive species awareness messages and laws. Hawai’i, for example, recorded 9.2 million visitors in 2022 (State of Hawai’i Department of Business, Economic Development, & Tourism, 2022). High visitor volume not only increases the amount of food and goods that must be imported (and are therefore opportunities for invasive species transport) but also increases the probability of people bringing foods, agricultural products, or goods that pose a risk but are not appropriately inspected or quarantined. In the Caribbean, people moving between islands have been ranked as a “high risk” for the intentional and unintentional spread of invasive species (Meissner et al., 2009; USDA APHIS, 2019). On average, the USVI welcomes around two million visitors per year, and more than 83% of hotel occupants are from the continental United States (USVI Bureau of Economic Research, 2024). As both international and U.S. continental visitations increase to Caribbean islands and the USVI, the probability of invasive species introduction is increased, yet the islands are chronically under-resourced at both the local and Federal levels. In addition, some islands receive a number of non-commercial vessels (e.g., small boats and charters) that are significantly less regulated in terms of cargo and conveyances, a gap that must be addressed. State, Federal, and international permits may be required for the movement of plant materials listed under the Lacey Act, Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES), or USDA. Without the capacity to inspect non-commercial vessels, however, the illegal transport of invasive species is unregulated and potentially facilitates the

movement of invasive species between the USVI, Puerto Rico, and nearby Caribbean Islands (e.g., the British Virgin Islands).

High military population flux due to changes of duty station and household moves creates significant risk of accidental invasive species introductions. For example, Hawai'i has the highest per-capita military and civilian defense personnel residents of any State (5.2%), a rate that is nearly 10 times greater than the State with the largest absolute number (California, 0.7%). The territory of Guam has an even higher percentage of the island's total population (5.9%) (Defense Manpower Data Center, 2024). This heavy military presence, in conjunction with the projected military buildup of activities and training in the Pacific, has resulted in region-, installation-, and base-specific plans to better address the risks, impacts, and need for coordination (U.S. Department of the Navy, 2015). Resulting from a 2015 USFWS biological opinion, the development and implementation of the Joint Region Marianas Biosecurity Program is an example of early detection, rapid response, inspections, decontamination, and more, not just for other DOD installations and regions, but other Federal agencies.

Failing to prevent invasive species establishment or address infestations on U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands also sets the stage for secondary invasions of other islands or continental areas (e.g., Bertelsmeier & Keller, 2018). This invasion dynamic can be vividly seen in the coconut rhinoceros beetle (CRB; *Oryctes rhinoceros*), a well-known pest of coconut and oil palms. The Hawaiian Islands were free from CRB until confirmed on the Island of O'ahu in 2013 and subsequently, from that single point of infestation, the beetle spread to the neighboring islands of Kaua'i, Hawai'i, and Maui by 2023 (Coconut Rhinoceros Beetle Response, 2024; Paudel et al. 2021). In 2017, CRB was also found on the island of Rota in the CNMI, likely from the same source as (or possibly from) O'ahu (Tay, unpublished data). Now only one domestic flight or ship away from the continental United States, CRB is an example of how failures of primary prevention, eradication, and active management within a single island can rapidly cascade into region-wide impacts. On the other hand, the brown treesnake program on Guam demonstrates how investments in strong interdiction efforts can prevent secondary invasions elsewhere (ISAC, 2023a).

1.2 Prevention Authorities

Some Federal agencies have specific authorities that allow them to regulate certain invasive species and taxonomic groups in not just terrestrial but also marine systems. For example, USDA is the lead agency that regulates foreign imports of agricultural and forestry commodities that pose a risk of becoming invasive or that may carry a pest that can cause significant harm to agriculture or natural resources. They accomplish this through a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) with CBP, which conducts the majority of inspections and enforces USDA regulations. However, there are examples of species and entire taxa that are not clearly identified under

any agency's authority and thus represent gaps, both on U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands and the continent. No Federal agency currently has the authority to restrict the importation of certain types of marine taxa, such as soft coral species, for example. The USFWS via the Lacey Act, meanwhile, has limited authority to regulate the importation and interstate movement of listed species of vertebrates, crustaceans, and mollusks as "injurious wildlife." The listing process has been arduous and economic considerations have, at times, outweighed invasion risk in some proposed listings. In addition, several species groups fall outside the boundaries of all Federal authorities, including spiders, soft corals, earthworms, and diseases specific to wildlife (Congressional Research Service, 2017).

The USDA has robust safeguarding and plant pest response programs with designated funding for incursions of high-priority pests of agriculture and forestry that are not already established in the United States. However, there is no parallel framework and funding for regionally important or non-agricultural priority invasive species that fall outside of USDA's purview, such as the spread of coqui frog (*Eleutherodactylus coqui*) outside of its native Puerto Rico. Without a coordinated effort between the Federal agencies and U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands to address gaps in jurisdictional authority, islands continue to be vulnerable to invasive species introductions.

2. MARINE BIOSECURITY

U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands contain a combined 3.8 million square miles of EEZ area, which includes fisheries and strategic military waters, as well as 84% of the coral reefs in the United States. Healthy coral reefs provide goods and services, including food, coastal protection, tourism, recreation, and biocultural uses valued at more than \$3.2 billion per year to Hawai'i, American Sāmoa, Guam, the CNMI, Puerto Rico, and the USVI (Brander & Van Beukering, 2013). Threats to coral reefs include coral bleaching, ocean acidification, and pollution, and each of these threats can have synergistic effects when combined with invasive species (Environmental Protection Agency [EPA], 2024a). While mangrove forests and seagrass beds are also crucial marine natural infrastructure and habitat on U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands, examples from coral reefs illustrate the urgent need for improved marine biosecurity.

2.1 Example: Stony Coral Tissue Loss Disease

Beginning in 2014, there were reports of an unknown coral disease killing multiple species of coral with up to a 90% mortality rate on some Florida and Caribbean reefs (Aeby et al., 2019; Alvarez-Filip et al., 2022). Although the causal pathogen (or pathogens) of stony coral tissue loss disease (SCTLD) has yet to be isolated and identified, experts agree that SCTLD is the most lethal coral disease on record. SCTLD is highly contagious and can be transmitted short distances

via direct contact between infected corals and through water circulation from nearby infected corals. The pathogen can also persist in sediments and reemerge to infect newly settled corals (Studivan et al., 2022). It has spread to 28 Caribbean countries and Territories and affected or killed more than 30 species of coral (Skrivernek & Wusinich-Mendez, 2020). The affected reefs are irrevocably changed, shifting in some areas from coral-dominated to algal-dominated reefs (Alvarez-Filip et al., 2019, 2022), and negatively impacting fish habitat, ecosystem services, and local economies (Swaminathan et al., 2024).

The pattern of long-distance, counter-current spread of SCTLD in Puerto Rico, the USVI, and neighboring Caribbean countries can only be explained by vessel traffic (Dahlgren et al., 2021; Rosenau et al., 2021). A study using simulated ballast water confirmed the potential for spread by vessels, and that UV ballast water treatment systems are only 50% effective at mitigating the SCTLD pathogen in water (Studivan et al., 2022). Research into the possibility of spread via biofilm, the initial bacterial slime layer that can carry other diseases and supports larger biofouling communities, is underway (Evans et al., 2022). This deadly coral disease is currently only found in the Caribbean (Atlantic and Gulf Rapid Reef Assessment, 2024), but there are concerns for global spread given the evidence for vessels as a pathway.

2.2 Vessel Ballast Water and Biofouling

Vessels have long been recognized as a substantial risk for transporting invasive species to islands in ballast tanks (Carlton, 1985; International Maritime Organization, 2024a) or as vessel biofouling growing attached to the hull or in protected niche areas (Davidson et al., 2014; International Maritime Organization, 2024b). A recent study projected that global maritime traffic will increase by as much as 1,209%, resulting in a 20-fold increase in global marine species invasion risk by 2050 (Sardain et al., 2019). A global review of primary detections of non-native aquatic species in marine, estuarine, and freshwater systems from 1965 to 2015 found that vessel ballast water and biofouling were the pathways responsible for most species movements (Bailey et al., 2020).

In the 1990s, global understanding and concern about invasive aquatic species movements with vessel ballast water led to concerted effort by the International Maritime Organization and individual countries, including the United States, to mitigate the risks with binding discharge standards, management practices, and new technologies to treat ballast water (Carlton, 1996; International Maritime Organization, 2024a). There are no parallel binding international mechanisms or agreements that compel the use of and maximum discharge standards for marine pollution control devices to maintain hulls and niche areas at a low biofilm or biofouling risk. However, the passage of the Federal Vessel Incidental Discharge Act (VIDA) in 2018 created a subsection of the Clean Water Act that required the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) to develop

uniform national discharge standards (EPA, 2024b) and the U.S. Coast Guard to develop a new regulatory framework for incidental discharges within two years. When the Coast Guard regulations are finalized, States and Territories will be preempted from keeping or passing different or more stringent regulations, including any ballast management, hull cleanliness, or no-discharge regulations, even if the final regulations do not provide protection against SCTLD. While VIDA includes three types of mechanisms for States and Territories to petition for a no-discharge zone, the only feasible mechanism is a petition for an emergency order requiring a “best management practice.” In addition, VIDA also specifies that the EPA must submit the request to the Coast Guard and receive a written agreement before granting or denying the emergency request within 180 days of receipt (S.140 – 115th Congress, 2018), a process and timeline that are not consistent with the emergency that SCTLD poses to U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands in the Pacific.

VIDA includes a requirement for review and updating every five years, which is an opportunity for the United States to set high but achievable standards and a regulatory framework that compels technology development and use to proactively manage vessel biofilm and prevent biofouling. The framework should mirror the Coast Guard regulations for testing, approving, and use of U.S. ballast water management systems. In addition, the U.S. Naval Research Laboratory conducts testing of ballast water management systems and the same approach should be applied for testing in-water cleaning systems that capture and remove pollutants, including invasive species, prior to discharging effluent.

2.3 Marine Aquarium Releases and “Outplanting”

A pathway analysis conducted by Bailey et al. (2020) showed that marine aquarium releases, mariculture escapes, and the purposeful “outplanting” of marine aquarium species as a cottage industry were a documented pathway for fewer introduction events when compared to ballast water and biofouling, yet the magnitude of harm from such events was no less serious (Atlantic and Gulf Rapid Reef Assessment, 2024). In the early 2000s, an aquarium keeper illegally outplanted a popular marine aquarium soft coral known as pulse coral (*Unomia stolonifera*) onto a Venezuela reef for future harvest as a cottage industry (Ruiz-Allais et al., 2014). The infestation has since spread across 60 miles of coastline at up to 80% coverage, killing hard corals, displacing other reef-dwelling species, and preventing the local regeneration of reef and seagrass ecosystems. This same species, despite its status as a State of Hawai’i regulated species that is illegal to possess, was found across nearly 80 acres during initial delimiting surveys in Pearl Harbor in 2023 and is likely the result of an aquarium release. In October 2023, a similar and popular marine aquarium species of soft coral native to the Red Sea called *Xenia umbellata* was discovered on shallow reefs off southwest Puerto Rico (Toledo-Rodriguez et al., 2024). Current retail sales of marine aquarium fish and invertebrates are valued at \$2.2 billion for approximately 55

million fish and invertebrates, numbers that are projected to increase and overshadow major fisheries such as tuna (Watson et al., 2023). The United States receives the highest volume of foreign imports of marine aquarium species in the world (Rhyne et al., 2017), which is largely unregulated internationally and nationally except for those species under CITES. These examples of soft coral invasions associated with the marine aquarium trade highlight the issue and need for addressing this pathway and infestations in marine environments.

2.4 Detection Tools for Marine Environments

Programs, capacity, methods, and tools for early detection and rapid response for marine invasive species are critically lacking (DOI, 2016; EPA, 2024c). Available techniques for environmental monitoring and detection include settling plates, benthic and plankton collection and identification, and visual or diver surveys, photo or video surveys where access is not restricted and water clarity allows. The two highest incidence pathways are associated with vessels, and despite improvements in detection and mitigation technologies it is reasonable to expect that these prevention mechanisms will not be 100% effective. Therefore, strong investments in detection tools, technologies, and programs in and around harbors and other likely areas should be a high priority.

3. CONTROL MEASURES AND LONG-TERM IMPACT REDUCTION

Many U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands already bear a heavy burden of invasive species due to their biogeography, colonial legacies, and global trade. These islands will experience additional native and endemic species losses, along with impacts to ecosystems, food production, economies, and human health if regulatory, policy, and implementation gaps are not addressed. In addition to the clear need for improved prevention capacity and authority described above, both biologically based and chemical controls, as well as post-disturbance restoration efforts for affected species, are urgently needed. These interventions can reduce the ongoing and ever-growing ecological and economic damage caused by invasive species while building resilience to other stressors, such as climate change.

3.1 Biologically Based Control Technologies

Biologically based control technologies (including classical biological control, genetic techniques like RNA interference and gene drives, bacterial mechanisms like *Wolbachia*, sterile or incompatible insect techniques, and others) can greatly reduce the economic, environmental, and human health impacts of invasive species. Some biological control agents (e.g., host-specific insects, parasites, and viruses, collectively referred to as “natural enemies”) become long term and self-sustaining population or transmission (vectoring) controls,

greatly reducing the environmental and financial costs over time when compared to intensive direct mechanical or chemical controls. Strong scientific research programs and regulatory safeguards support targeted approaches that are highly species-specific and effective (Sheppard et al., 2020).

The development of new or locally appropriate biologically based control technologies and the necessary infrastructure to support those technologies is particularly needed on islands. Mechanical or chemical controls that otherwise might be viable alternatives can be prohibitively expensive, must usually be imported over long distances, and island communities may lack the capacity or approval to utilize them. A major impediment to the release of biologically based controls in more island locations is the lack of specialized facilities and capacity needed to test the safety and efficacy of controls for new release locations, as well as the associated need for local facilities to breed, cultivate, or synthesize the controls prior to release. On-island infrastructure and expertise can also support proactive research to identify likely invasive species arrivals, screen for natural enemies, and conduct host-specificity testing to prepare for invasive species before they arrive.

The rapid development of biologically based control techniques specific to island concerns is needed to protect island ecosystems, agricultural commodities, and cultural resources. The success of this approach is illustrated by the exploration for and testing of a classical biological control for the erythrina gall wasp (*Quadrastichus erythrinae*). This invasive species was detected in Hawai'i in 2005 and threatened the extinction of the native wiliwili tree (*Erythrina sandwicensis*). In response, *Eurytoma erythrinae*, a parasitoid wasp that preys upon the eggs of the erythrina gall wasp, was sourced from East Africa, brought into containment for testing, and approved in 2008 for release. Post-release evaluations indicate that biological control of erythrina gall wasp has been successful in reducing pest densities and tree mortality, thereby contributing to the long-term conservation of this endemic island species (Kaufman et al., 2020).

Sterile insect technique (SIT) is also a proven management strategy for some widespread, harmful invasive species on U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands. There are limited facilities and capacity on the Hawaiian Islands, however, and the lack of facilities on other U.S. and U.S.-affiliated Islands is even more severe, so collaboration, support, and access may not be sufficient to address existing or emerging invasive species control needs as they arise. The only SIT production facility in Hawai'i, for example, is on O'ahu and operated by the California Department of Food and Agriculture. It produces Mediterranean fruit fly males (*Ceratitidis capitata*) that are sterilized and shipped to California for release. Additionally, while some biological control facilities in the continental United States and other nations (e.g., Mexico, Guatemala, and Fiji) can be used to support island needs, these are important complements to, not replacements for, island-specific infrastructure and capacity.

Whether for threatened and endangered species, to maintain the viability of agricultural production, or to protect culturally or economically important species, additional facilities to support local research, development, and large-scale rearing and production are needed to achieve success with many forms of biologically based control technologies at the scale required for ecological and/or economic restoration.

3.2 Chemical Control Technologies

The use of pesticides and other chemical controls plays a significant role in invasive species management programs on islands, especially related to early detections of newly established plants and invertebrates. In many situations, chemical controls are the most effective tools for swift and targeted response due to their rapid availability, scalable costs, and immediate impacts. A global review of invasive plant management in ecological restoration found over 42% of the restoration projects relied on herbicides to accomplish their goals, including restoration efforts in vulnerable areas such as endangered species habitat (Weidlich et al., 2020).

Using pesticides in island ecological systems can present issues from both methodology and regulatory perspectives. In general, most pesticides are researched and labeled for use on urban, public health, or agricultural invasive species, and there is limited research and labeling available for products to address conservation applications in island ecosystems. Additionally, the labeled application methods typically do not consider topography, climate, vegetative cover, and other conditions unique to islands. For all new application types—whether on U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands or in continental ecosystems—researching and labeling new products for use on emerging pests or weeds is costly and there is little incentive for a chemical company to register or assist with registering a product for small markets. This high barrier to entry can limit industry’s interest in pursuing new products or expanding the use (labeling) of existing ones to new target species or conditions, all of which may be necessary to effectively address invasive species in the island context. Additionally, the EPA’s re-registration process for established active ingredients can impede the continued use of existing necessary and effective pesticides. For example, to re-register Rotenone, the only piscicide used for invasive fish management nationally, for use in any future context will cost an additional \$1 million, which may not be feasible for an active ingredient with small markets, such as islands.

Future re-registrations of existing pesticides on U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands will also be impacted by the EPA’s Endangered Species Act workplan for non-target species (EPA, 2022). Historically, the EPA has used “cost-benefit” analysis when registering and re-registering active ingredients. The new strategy will require a more thorough EPA Section 7 (a) (2) consultation with USFWS and NOAA that will emphasize possible toxicity and non-target impacts to endangered species and the destruction of critical habitat, but possibly without an evaluation of how the active ingredients can

protect vulnerable species from the negative effects of habitat degradation, predation, competition, and spread of disease caused by invasive species.

3.3 Control Tools for Marine Environments

Historically, a significant amount of the funding and capacity for developing control tools and methods for terrestrial invasive species originated from agricultural and forestry sector investment, which then benefits natural resource protection. However, the same constituencies that fund and support Federal investment in research and development capacity are not present for marine invasive species. This has resulted in the lack of necessary tools and methods that can be applied quickly and at appropriate scales in marine environments. Control options to date have been limited to smothering with tarps and manual removal. While effective, these control tools are arduous and temporary when infestations are large. Soft corals like *Unomia* and *Xenia* can easily fragment, drift to new areas as biofouling, and quickly re-attach to new areas and form new infestations (Ruiz-Allais et al., 2021). In addition, while the Clean Water Act is vital for many environmental reasons, the high cost of testing is a barrier to the registration and use of control tools for marine environments. Test results must also be demonstrated in spaces that are representative of the islands where they will be deployed. Given the lack of clear regulatory authority around certain marine taxa, these early detection and control tools, as well as outreach, are vitally important.

3.4 Post-Disturbance Restoration

When prevention efforts have failed and invasive species are widespread on islands, serious long-term investments and novel approaches may be needed to facilitate restoration and recovery after disturbances and to prevent reinvasion (Reaser et al., 2007). Passive ecosystem restoration methods, such as the removal or exclusion of herbivores, may not be sufficient if the damage is severe (Chazdon et al., 2021; Luna-Mendoza et al., 2019) or a rapid response is needed (Zahawi et al., 2014). U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands are also disproportionately impacted by climate change and are projected to experience increases in both the severity and frequency of extreme storms, droughts, wildfires, and other hazards (Frazier et al., 2023; Méndez-Lazaro et al., 2023). With these impacts, there is a greater likelihood of newly facilitated or transported invasions or the rapid establishment of invasive species after a disaster. Active and timely restoration planting and management to control invasive grasses, on the other hand, has improved wildfire recovery outcomes on islands like the Hawaiian archipelago (Trauernicht et al., 2018).

Many U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands lack the capacity, infrastructure, and tools for both rapid and long-term restoration efforts. Effective restoration efforts require access to facilities that are specific to the ecosystem, cultural, workforce, and/or research needs. Existing examples of this necessary infrastructure include reforestation stock

nurseries like the Cambalache Tree Nursery in Puerto Rico, threatened animal breeding facilities like Hawai'i's Maui Bird Conservation Center, and food and cultural plant nurseries. Tools such as seed collection and storage capacity, seedling production, workforce development, and optimized pre-and post-planting protocols are also required (for estimates of needs related to forest restoration in the continental United States, see Fargione et al., 2021). In some cases, the impacts of invasive species may also necessitate the development of resistant host populations, as is the case in Hawai'i with the endemic 'ōhi'a (*Metrosideros polymorpha*) and koa (*Acacia koa*) trees and their respective invasive fungal pathogens, the "rapid 'ōhi'a death" fungus (*Ceratocystis lukuohia*) and koa fusarium fungus (*Fusarium oxysporum*). These endemic island species require long-term support for research and development programs specific to their endemic ranges if they are to persist.

Laboratories, rearing and containment facilities, and integrated community engagement in invasive species response also support human health and disaster preparedness. This reflects the One Health approach, in which wildlife and ecosystem health are integral components of human health and global disease control (Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies, 2022; Mackenzie & Jeggo, 2019). Illustrative island cases in support of a One Health approach include invasive rat control campaigns to reduce leptospirosis, giant African snail (*Lissachatina fulica*) eradication to prevent transmission of rat lungworm disease, small Indian mongoose (*Herpestes auro-punctatus*) control to reduce reservoirs for rabies virus, and *Wolbachia*-infected mosquito programs to control for mosquitoes that can spread Zika, dengue, chikungunya, and human and avian malaria.

Because the tools and models developed for restoration at scale in the continental United States are often not feasible or applicable in islands, specialized methods are needed that recognize their unique ecological conditions (e.g., topography, diversity of microclimates, soils), species, and cultural values. Increasing and developing capacity for post-disturbance restoration, particularly locally adapted strategies developed with climate-informed decision frameworks, such as "Resist-Accept-Direct" (Lynch et al., 2021) and "Resistance, Resilience, Transition" (Nagel et al., 2017), can build the resilience of native landscapes to invasive species, climate change, and future disasters.

Detailed maps, geospatial and climate data at relevant scales, and coordinated risk assessments on priority species and high-risk pathways tailored to islands are also needed to ensure these restoration efforts are effectively planned, sited, and implemented for current and future conditions. For example, the National Land Cover Database offers up-to-date nationwide land cover data for the continental United States, but information sources like this for the U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands are often absent, outdated, or not relevant to local conditions.

4. ISLAND-SPECIFIC SOCIAL AND CAPACITY CONDITIONS

Communities on U.S. island Territories and the Freely Associated States have a history of, and in some ways continue to be, used as testing grounds, referred to as "second-class citizens," and denied public benefits provided to States (Maurer & Hogue, 2020; Ciolli & Hrelac, 2022; Hammond, 2021). At the same time, Federal short-term assignments and work travel to U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands can be denied for fear of the appearance of a "junket." This has resulted in a long-term lack of information exchange, trust building, professional development, and interagency connections for both Federal and local employees. On U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands, Federal agencies, including those with invasive species prevention and management responsibilities, have been historically understaffed and face challenges in recruiting and retaining staff (U.S. Government Accountability Office, 2024). These challenges reduce Federal agency effectiveness, actionable research, management activities, and island-specific knowledge.

4.1. Social and Historical Concerns Surrounding Invasive Species

Some historical introductions of invasive species for purposes like agriculture, erosion control, sport, and biological control have worsened invasive species burdens on U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands (Ewel et al., 1999; Beard et al., 2017; Moody et al., 2021). The legacy of these pre-regulation and/or indiscriminate introductions has created distrust by island communities towards actions and proposals put forward by outside entities, including Federal agencies. Advancing all elements of the priority action areas in this paper requires investments in Federal-to-local discourse, layperson and professional education, and collaborative approaches that respect island cultural and social concerns.

4.2. Island Capacity for Invasive Species Management

Supporting sufficient capacity for research, implementation, and long-term invasive species management is a challenge for all U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands. Even when Federal assistance or cooperative agreements are available to island communities, local agencies and entities may be unable to access funds due to a lack of staff capacity for grant applications and reporting requirements, limited English fluency, and/or an inability to procure matching funds. Some programs have tackled these issues successfully, such as the National Fish and Wildlife Foundation's America the Beautiful Challenge Territorial and Tribal Assistance program, California Technical Assistance Program, and U.S. Forest Service Community Navigators. These programs should be emulated and extended to assist in more direct capacity support for Federal applications, reporting, and related administrative processes to increase access of U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands to Federal funding sources that can add local capacity.

Recommendations

Based on the above findings and summaries of the unique challenges that invasive species bring to U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands, the ISAC offers the following recommendations.

1. EXPAND FEDERAL SUPPORT OF INVASIVE SPECIES COORDINATION

Invasive species concerns, concepts, and actions must be fully integrated into efforts to address climate resilience, food security, economies, cultural concerns, and biodiversity, as well as international assistance and geopolitical strategies related to U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands. The existing strengths of Federal, State, Territorial, and local partnerships should be formalized and amplified through agreements with greater attention to island biology, culture, jurisdiction, capacity, and cross-coordinating bodies.

- a. **ISAC recommends that Federal agencies support, participate in, and in some cases convene integrated Federal-State/Territory-local councils or similar bodies on each island that can address invasive species concerns with self-determination and autonomy. They should formalize their participation in these coordinating bodies with MOUs (or similar) and seek opportunities to fund interventions that are identified.** In some cases, this may be an invasive species council (e.g., the Guam Invasive Species Council); in others, another mechanism or body may be appropriate. The creation and/or increased support and funding of integrated councils will ensure Federal investments are efficient and cost-effective and will better leverage existing expertise, funding, data management, and authorities. It will also elevate the profile of their importance. The existing Regional Response Teams for environmental incident response that are co-chaired by the EPA and the Coast Guard could serve as a precedent for a National standard on coordination.
- b. **ISAC recommends empowering invasive species councils to co-create island specific risk assessments for pathways, invasive species of concern, or inbound commodities,** integrating current situational analysis and future climate modeling. In addition, ISAC recommends a gap analysis of what resources are available for invasive species management on the continental United States that are currently not being collected or created for islands, and timely action should be taken to fill those resource gaps.
- c. **ISAC recommends that Federal agencies actively engage with and champion the relevant entities described in existing international and regional compacts, strategies, and communiqués to advance shared priorities.** These include the Regional Biosecurity Plan for Micronesia and Hawai'i (RBP), Strategic Action

Plans from the 2022 Pacific Ecological Security Conference (PESC), and the Greater Caribbean Safeguarding Initiative (GCSI). They call on agencies (USDA, DOI, DOD, Department of Commerce, the United States Agency for International Development [USAID], and DHS) to support and advance invasive species prevention and management efforts to protect U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands (MIF, 2023, 2024a, 2024b; PESC, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; USDA, 2024b; U.S. Department of the Navy, 2015).

- d. **ISAC recommends that the U.S. Department of State, USAID, DHS, the Peace Corps, and other relevant Federal agencies work together to incorporate, prioritize, and fund invasive species actions in their climate change strategies, development planning, and diplomatic goals in island regions worldwide.** This is urgent given the notable high-level importance of invasive species to Pacific Island country and Territory leaders for climate resilience, food security, cultural resources, quality of life, and sustainable development (MIF, 2024a, 2024b).
- e. **ISAC recommends that the Department of Health and Human Services, USDA, DOI, DHS, and other relevant Federal departments and agencies work together and with local partners and agencies to incorporate invasive species management into existing public health and biodefense strategies.** These should recognize that microbes and their vectors can often be invasive species.
- f. **ISAC recommends cross-agency collaborative opportunities be identified, and appropriate mechanisms established (e.g., MOUs or similar agreements), to maximize efficiency, efficacy, and capacity.** On Guam, for example, this could include an interagency agreement enabling the cross-training of brown treesnake detection dogs for inspections for more than one target (e.g. CRB, little fire ant [*Wasmannia auropunctata*]). The National Island Restoration MOU between 10 Federal and non-Federal signatories to promote an integrated and coordinated approach to protecting, managing, and restoring islands provides an example of such cooperation around shared objectives (USFWS, 2024b).
- g. **ISAC recommends that the USDA acts to enable the United States to become an active nation and/or official member in the two Regional Plant Protection Organizations that are relevant to the U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands: the Caribbean Agricultural Health and Food Safety Agency (CAHFSA) and the Pacific Plant Protection Organization (PPPO).** The interests of Hawai'i, Florida, and the Gulf states would be best served not just

by State and Territorial participation, but also Federal participation and membership. The existing strengths of the Federally led GCSI should be advanced via engagement within the CAHFSA, which is a member organization of the GCSI. The needs of Caribbean islands and nations would be more thoroughly met with this multilevel approach.

- h. **ISAC recommends that a non-competitive rapid response fund for Federal and State entities to engage in island-based response be established and maintained.** For invasive species established on an island where the tools and capacity for eradication or active management are feasible elsewhere, **parallel eradication or parallel management on the affected island should be supported by a strong Federal response.** Eradication or active management of invasive species on a single island should be considered prevention for other islands and the continental United States due to secondary infestations. This recommendation benefits not only the islands themselves, but also the most likely (due to climatic matching) continental regions to be affected by primary establishments on islands, such as California, the Gulf states, and the southeastern Atlantic states.

2. ENHANCE PROGRAMS, PARTNERSHIPS, TOOLS, AND PLACE-BASED EFFORTS FOR PREVENTION

Islands should be empowered to implement better protections from invasive species arriving via passenger travel, cargo and conveyances, military affiliated actions, and household moves, regardless of international or domestic points of origin. Prevention efforts should match the scope and scale of the unique island context.

- a. **ISAC recommends that CBP, APHIS, and other Federal agencies enhance services and actions for prevention from foreign sources, inclusive of entering into new or renewed MOUs where requested with local border protection entities. Federal agencies should prioritize the renewal and enhancement of necessary MOUs.** On some U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands where Federal agencies have jurisdiction over inbound and transshipped foreign goods, there are few or no locally based Federal agency staff to conduct inspections or take regulatory actions.
- b. **ISAC recommends mandatory inspection of domestic inbound and outbound goods and traveler possessions through interagency collaboration, MOUs, facilities sharing, and other mechanisms.** The APHIS inspection program for pre-departure from Hawai'i to the continental United States continent is an example of the support that is needed by the Federal Government for goods and visitors arriving to U.S. Territories and Hawai'i.

- c. **ISAC recommends that APHIS, CBP, USFWS, and other relevant Federal agencies identify sharable information and create a data access system (protected informational portal), data use agreements, and communications plan to exchange information with appropriate State and Territory-based agencies.** Existing port of entry information systems, such as sharable parts of Emergency Action Notifications generated by CBP and APHIS, would be highly useful to island governments and agencies in real time. The current barriers to sharing information, including ineffective and irregular systems, could be improved if mutually workable solutions were prioritized. Information sharing between Federal inspection agencies and State and Territorial agencies will improve the ability of all parties to respond to an invasive species of local concern as early and effectively as possible. These should be integrated into Siren: The National Early Detection and Rapid Response Information System to respect the needs of legal issues (e.g., Protected Trade Information) while allowing a channel of timely communication.
- d. **Pest risk committees should be established, have a standing Federal agency representative membership inclusive of DHS, DOD, NOAA, USDA, USFWS, and have a regular meeting schedule as part of all major port of entry standard operating procedures.** These should represent each island port (or grouping of ports) and incorporate state priorities into Federal agency priorities for situational awareness.
- e. **ISAC recommends that mechanisms that allow Federal port of entry agencies the ability to implement and enforce island-specific prevention priorities (e.g., FRSMMP) be updated and streamlined to be responsive to island needs.** For jurisdictions where no such program exists, the responsible Federal entity should scope and implement new programs that would allow for the Federal recognition of state- and island- managed programs for a species or spatial environment. Further, **the Hawai'i Ant Policy should be used as an exemplar of a policy allowing Federal inspection agencies to stop foreign imports containing ant species and a broad suite of potentially harmful species.**
- f. **ISAC recommends funding the Coastal Aquatic Invasive Species Mitigation Grant Program authorized by VIDA to assist all jurisdictions with inspection, monitoring, and enforcement programs,** as also recommended by the Washington Department of Fish and Wildlife (Turner, 2024) and the Aquatic Invasive Species Commission (Aquatic Invasive Species Commission, 2023). There is a significant lack of Federal, State, and Territorial co-enforcement capacity once VIDA is enacted.

- g. **ISAC recommends that additional improvements be made to DOD operations, including the drafting and implementation of biosecurity plans for all existing and planned island installations and operating locations**, with protocols for operations and training exercises, as well as contractors, military and civilian personnel, and dependents. **DOD should continue to address capability gaps and invest in sufficient and consistent biosecurity-related infrastructure and capabilities** to ensure cleanliness standards are met for all inbound and outbound military materiel at military installations and operating locations in the Indo-Pacific (e.g., Armed Forces Pest Management Board, 2021).
- h. **ISAC recommends that other Federal agencies evaluate, adopt, and implement DOD's robust cleanliness standards, biosecurity protocols, and on-site mitigations as exemplars for invasive species prevention and risk management.**

3. ADDRESS GAPS IN FEDERAL AUTHORITIES FOR PREVENTION, EARLY DETECTION, AND RAPID RESPONSE

There are often regulatory gaps where one island jurisdiction ends and another begins. This problem is especially acute with regard to a lack of authority to regulate the importation of multiple marine invertebrate taxa (Jewell, 2020), as well as some non-agricultural terrestrial species (e.g., invasive earthworms) and freshwater species.

- a. **ISAC recommends that the National Invasive Species Council (NISC) work with the Aquatic Nuisance Species Task Force and others to clarify regulatory gaps in U.S. authorities for prevention** and articulate a path forward to fill those gaps.
- b. **The USFWS and NOAA should engage with U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands to determine how the Lacey Act Amendments of 1981 could be utilized for cooperative law enforcement efforts to prevent the introduction of invasive species that are prohibited or restricted.**
- c. **ISAC recommends that the USFWS, CBP, DOD, and other relevant Federal agencies support island efforts to enforce local invasive species and wildlife offenses by sharing information and working together**, similar to the 2019 MOU signed by the Great Lakes St. Lawrence Governors & Premiers (Great Lakes St. Lawrence Governors & Premiers, 2019).
- d. **ISAC recommends that the NISC and member agencies continue the development of the National EDRR Framework**, including securing permanent annual funding for EDRR to protect wildlife and habitats.

4. DEVELOP CONTROL TOOLS FOR REDUCING THE IMPACTS OF ESTABLISHED INVASIVE SPECIES

Control tools for invasive species that are established on U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands must support the needs of those islands. This may require research and development of new biologically based control mechanisms, new safety and efficacy testing for pesticides and herbicides, increased chemical control registration flexibility, automated early detection tools such as machine learning or AI-based image recognition, or different implementation and regulatory mechanisms.

- a. **ISAC recommends that Federal agencies lead the research and registration of chemical, mechanical, and other control tools for the prevention (e.g., in-water cleaning with capture and treatment to proactively manage biofilm) and control of invasive species impacting islands (e.g., soft corals, pathogens and fungi affecting native forest species).** While development, testing, and registration of terrestrial chemical and mechanical control tools are largely borne or subsidized by agriculture and forestry industries or public health agencies, there is little to no parallel research and development pathway for control tools for use in the marine environment.
- b. **ISAC recommends that the USDA and other Federal agencies continue to identify and address shared challenges and opportunities for biological control**, including implementing the Pacific Biological Control Strategic Action Plan (PESC, 2022a) and taking parallel actions to address biological control needs for Puerto Rico and the USVI. Federal leadership, research, and infrastructure to expand the use of biological control technology are needed to address the impacts of invasive species specific to tropical ecosystems on U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands. Islands will also benefit from Federal engagement on the development and use of advanced biotechnologies (Executive Office of the President, 2022a), as well as other novel control technologies for widespread harmful invasive species, such as malaria-vectoring mosquitoes, CRB, ants, rodents, and reptiles. **Federal agencies should deepen their commitments to collaborating on the science and implementation of biological controls, including advanced biotechnologies**, addressing these problematic groups of invasive species.
- c. **ISAC encourages the NISC to address barriers and needs for increasing the use and availability of biological controls as tools, with particular attention to islands that are heavily invaded.** This may include a new biological control white paper (e.g., ISAC, 2015, 2016).
- d. **ISAC recommends that the EPA and USFWS incorporate the beneficial impacts of pesticides for protecting threatened and endangered species and**

associated habitats into the Section 7 consultation process for the registration and re-registration of pesticides. Because the testing of pesticides for continental systems does not factor in local island conditions or varying jurisdictional authorities, **ISAC recommends increases in local technical capacity to ensure sound science and regulatory expertise.** Unintended consequences could occur if there is not flexibility in procedures, especially in use areas where invasive and endangered species intersect.

5. MEET ISLAND-SPECIFIC NEEDS FOR RESTORATION AND LONG-TERM RECOVERY

Well-funded research and the infrastructure to implement long-term restoration and recovery are central to reducing and managing invasive species impacts on islands. Infrastructure should have ample and flexible use of space, be modernized to meet best practices, and should not be centralized, as actual local conditions are part of the required natural infrastructure.

- a. **ISAC recommends that new and upgraded infrastructure and long-term staff capacity be created and co-designed according to the needs of island communities and governments.** Facilities should take local ecological conditions into account, be integrated into the local communities to create long-lasting workforce opportunities, create ecological and disaster resilience redundancy for threatened and endangered species, and use inter-agency agreements to share resources and layer local initiatives under a One Health approach.

6. IMPROVE EDUCATION, OUTREACH, AND COMMUNICATION

There is inconsistent usage of Federally backed programs such as “Don’t Pack a Pest” across all U.S. and U.S.-affiliated jurisdictions, both on islands as well as continental areas. Ongoing research and data would better inform what programs are being utilized or should be expanded, or identify voluntary programs that are *not* being utilized and thus other investments would be more effective.

- a. **ISAC recommends that preventative programs like “Don’t Pack a Pest” and “Hungry Pests” be institutionally supported, expanded, improved with the use of ongoing social science research, and made consistent** in terms of their presence at all island-relevant and continental ports of entry for air and sea travelers. **ISAC also recommends expanded Federal focus on the “Don’t Let it Loose” message and programs, including greater attention to marine aquarium and pet trade audiences.**
- b. **ISAC recommends that a consistent outreach program covering all species associated with civilian, Federal**

service, and military household moves be integrated into the requirements and certification processes for household moving and shipping companies, inclusive of all U.S. military contractors and DOD documentation. Currently, passenger-based education does not suit this pathway’s needs. USDA and State-led programs oriented to household moves, such as those directed at specific continental invasive species (e.g., spongy moth [*Lymantria dispar*], spotted lanternfly [*Lycorma delicatula*]), should be evaluated and harmonized into this broader and more consistent approach.

- c. **ISAC recommends that Federal agencies improve invasive species awareness and outreach through tailored “tabletop” exercises with the relevant response groups** (e.g., regulatory authorities, non-profits, academic institutions, Federal agencies outside of their typical professional space). This would establish workflows, enhance awareness, and synchronize efforts, as well as provide staff and scientists with ongoing professional training and support (NISC, 2024).
- d. **ISAC recommends that Federal agencies provide support for professional educational opportunities for islanders (e.g., “train the trainer” activities and career pathways).** The Office of Insular Affairs Pacific Island regional biosecurity training program is a successful example of Federal assistance across complex jurisdictions (State, Territory, Freely Associated State) to achieve professional training, communication, and coordination. Additional training opportunities and support for professionals are needed for best management practices in control and eradication.

7. UNDERSTAND AND SUPPORT ISLAND COMMUNITY NEEDS

U.S. and U.S.-affiliated island experts and communities are aware of their unique needs, challenges, and what points of collaboration with Federal agencies will be the most welcome and effective. Each island’s invasive species context differs, and successful collaboration requires deep engagement and a willingness to act when local concerns are elevated to federal agency partners.

- a. **ISAC recommends that Federal agencies support social science research and outreach to increase local awareness of invasive species impacts and address concerns about the removal or eradication of invasive species, as well as the efficacy and current safeguards on control mechanisms.** This should include the contributions of Indigenous knowledge and will encourage co-creation, mutual understanding, and collaboration around management efforts, and ensure environmentally just outcomes pursuant to Executive Order 14096 (Executive Office of the President, 2022b, 2023).

- b. **ISAC recommends that Federal agencies enable local capacity by making available professional translation assistance, grant writing and administration technical assistance, match waivers, and direct assistance programs for grants and agreements** in jurisdictions

where these barriers are an impediment to accessing Federal programs and funding (ISAC, 2023b). These programs will be most successful if accompanied by effective communication strategies to ensure they are not underutilized.

Conclusion

This paper outlines the priority action areas needed to address some of the most pressing Federal regulatory, policy, and implementation gaps around invasive species affecting U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands. The recommendations are urgent, feasible, and actionable, and refer to invasive species issues of general importance to the entire United States. U.S. and U.S.-affiliated islands ecosystems and people are equally deserving of the benefits that the continental States receive with respect to terrestrial and marine biosecurity, long-term impact reduction measures, and local consultation, consideration, and capacity. Without Federal leadership and coordination in addressing invasive species issues across all geographies—including U.S. and U.S. affiliated islands—invasive species will continue to undermine the Nation’s security, climate resilience and adaptation strategies, economy, natural resources, cultural heritage, food security, public health systems, and defense capabilities.

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References

- Aeby, G. S., Ushijima, B., Campbell, J. E., Jones, S., Williams, G. J., Meyer, J. L., Häse, C., & Paul, V. J. (2019). Pathogenesis of a tissue loss disease affecting multiple species of corals along the Florida reef tract. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6, 678. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00678>
- Aquatic Invasive Species Commission. (2023). Improving the Prevention, Eradication, Control and Mitigation of Aquatic Invasive Species (AIS). Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.trcp.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Aquatic-Invasive-Species-Report-3-28-2023.pdf>
- Armed Forces Pest Management Board. (2021). Technical Guide 31: Operational Washdown and Agricultural Inspection Preparation for Military Conveyances and Equipment. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.acq.osd.mil/eie/afpmb/docs/techguides/tg31.pdf>
- Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies. (2022). The Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies and the One Health Approach: Providing the Foundation for a Leadership Role. Accessed 18 November 2024. https://www.fishwildlife.org/application/files/4616/6844/3262/AFWA_and_the_One_Health_Approach_-_Providing_the_Foundation_for_a_Leadership_Role_07_11_22.pdf
- Alvarez-Filip, L., Estrada-Saldívar, N., Pérez-Cervantes, E., Molina-Hernández, A., & González-Barrios, F. J. (2019). A rapid spread of the stony coral tissue loss disease outbreak in the Mexican Caribbean. *PeerJ*, 7, e8069. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.8069>
- Alvarez-Filip, L., González-Barrios, F. J., Pérez-Cervantes, E., Molina-Hernández, A., & Estrada-Saldívar, N. (2022). Stony coral tissue loss disease decimated Caribbean coral populations and reshaped reef functionality. *Communications Biology* 5, 440. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-022-03398-6>
- Atlantic and Gulf Rapid Reef Assessment. (2024). Coral Disease Outbreak. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.agrra.org/coral-disease-outbreak/>
- Bailey, S. A., Brown, L., Campbell, M. L., Canning-Clode, J., Carlton, J. T., Castro, N., Chainho, P., Chan, F. T., Creed, J. C., Curd, A., Darling, J. A., Fofonoff, P. W., Galil, B. S., Hewitt, C. L., Inglis, G. J., Keith, I., Mandrak, N. E., Marchini, A., McKenzie, C. H., Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A., Ojaveer, H., Pires, A., Robinson, T. B., Ruiz, G. M., Seaward, K., Son, M. O., Therriault, T. W., & Zhan, A. (2020). Trends in the detection of aquatic non-indigenous species across global marine, estuarine and freshwater ecosystems: A 50-year perspective. *Diversity and Distributions*, 26(12), 1780–1797. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.13167>
- Beard, K. H., Johnson, S. A., & Shiels, A. B. (2017). Frogs: Coqui frogs, greenhouse frogs, Cuban tree frogs, and cane toads. In Pitt, W. C., Beasley, J. C., & Witmer, G. W. (Eds.), *Ecology and Management of Terrestrial Vertebrate Invasive Species in the United States* (pp. 163–192). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315157078-9>
- Bellard, C., Cassey, P., & Blackburn, T. M. (2016). Alien species as a driver of recent extinctions. *Biology Letters*, 12(2), 20150623. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2015.0623>
- Bertelsmeier, C., & Keller, L. (2018). Bridgehead effects and role of adaptive evolution in invasive populations. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 33(7), 527–534. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2018.04.014>
- Brander, L. M., & Van Beukering, P. (2013). The Total Economic Value of U.S. Coral Reefs: A Review of the Literature. NOAA Coral Reef Conservation Program, Silver Spring, MD. Accessed 18 November 2024. https://www.coris.noaa.gov/activities/economic_value/
- Brewington, L., Eichelberger, B., Read, N., Parsons, E., Kerkering, H., Martin, C., Miles, W., Idechong, J., & Burgett, J. (2023). Pacific Island perspectives on invasive species and climate change. In Walsh, S. J., Mena, C. F., Stewart, J. R., & Muñoz Pérez, J. P. (Eds.) *Island Ecosystems. Social and Ecological Interactions in the Galapagos Islands* (pp. 59–78). Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-28089-4_5
- Brewington, L., Rodgers, L., & Greenwood, L. (2024). Recommendations for incorporating invasive species into U.S. climate change adaptation planning and policy. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 6(9), e13210. <https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.13210>
- Carlton, J. T. (1985). Transoceanic and interoceanic dispersal of coastal marine organisms: The biology of ballast water. *Oceanography and Marine Biology: An Annual Review*, 23, 313–371.
- Carlton, J. T. (1996). Pattern, process, and prediction in marine invasion ecology. *Biological Conservation*, 78(1-2), 97-106. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207\(96\)00020-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207(96)00020-1)
- Chazdon, R. L., Falk, D. A., Banin, L. F., Wagner, M., Wilson, S. J., Grabowski, R. C., & Suding, K. N. (2021). The intervention continuum in restoration ecology: Rethinking the active–passive dichotomy. *Restoration Ecology*, 32(8), e13535. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rec.13535>
- Ciulli, A. M., & Hrelac, D. M. (2022). Third-class citizens: Unequal protection within United States territories. *Suffolk University Law Review*, 55, 179. https://www.pullcom.com/media/publication/362_THIRD-CLASS%20CITIZENS%20UNEQUAL%20PROTECTION%20WITHIN%20UNITED%20STATES%20TERRITORIES.pdf
- Coconut Rhinoceros Beetle Response. (2024). Frequently Asked Questions. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.crbhawaii.org/faq>
- Code of Federal Regulations §318.13.8. (n.d.). Regulations on the Movement of Plants. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-7/subtitle-B/chapter-III/part-318/subpart-A/section-318.13-8>
- Congressional Research Service. (2017). *Invasive Species: Major Laws and the Role of Selected Federal Agencies*. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://crsreports.congress.gov/product/pdf/R/R43258/7>

- Dahlgren, C. P., Pizarro, V., Sherman, K., Greene, W., & Oliver, J. (2021). Spatial and temporal patterns of stony coral tissue loss disease outbreaks in the Bahamas. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 682114. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.682114>
- Davidson, I., Ruiz, G., & Gorgula, S. (2014). Vessel Biofouling in Hawaii: Current Patterns of a Potent Marine Bioinvasion Vector and Potential Management Solutions. Report to the Department of Land and Natural Resources (DLNR), Coordinating Group on Alien Pest Species (CGAPS), and the Hauoli Mau Loa Foundation. Honolulu, Hawaii. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://dlnr.hawaii.gov/hisc/files/2013/05/FINAL-Hawaii-biofouling-report-2014.pdf>
- Defense Manpower Data Center. (2024). DoD Personnel, Workforce Reports & Publications. June 2024 report. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://dwp.dmdc.osd.mil/dwp/app/dod-data-reports/workforce-reports>
- Environmental Protection Agency [EPA]. (2022). ESA Workplan Update: Nontarget Species Mitigation for Registration Review and Other FIFRA Actions. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.epa.gov/system/files/documents/2022-11/esa-workplan-update.pdf>
- Environmental Protection Agency [EPA]. (2024a). Threats to Coral Reefs. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.epa.gov/coral-reefs/threats-coral-reefs>
- Environmental Protection Agency [EPA]. (2024b). Vessel Incidental Discharge National Standards of Performance. Federal Register 82074. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2024-10-09/pdf/2024-22013.pdf>
- Environmental Protection Agency [EPA]. (2024c). Detecting and Monitoring Aquatic Invasive Species. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.epa.gov/water-research/detecting-and-monitoring-aquatic-invasive-species>
- Evans, J. S., Paul, V. J., & Kellogg, C. A. (2022). Biofilms as potential reservoirs of stony coral tissue loss disease. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9, 1009407. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.1009407>
- Executive Office of the President. (2022a). Executive Order 14081: Advancing Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing Innovation for a Sustainable, Safe, and Secure American Bioeconomy (Sept. 15, 2022). Federal Register 56849. <https://www.federalregister.gov/d/2022-20167>
- Executive Office of the President. (2022b). Memorandum: Implementation of Guidance for Federal Departments and Agencies on Indigenous Knowledge. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/IK-Guidance-Implementation-Memo.pdf>
- Executive Office of the President. (2023). Executive Order 14096: Revitalizing Our Nation's Commitment to Environmental Justice for All (April 23, 2023). Federal Register 25251. <https://www.federalregister.gov/d/2023-08955>
- Ewel, J. J., O'Dowd, D. J., Bergelson, J., Daehler, C. C., D'Antonio, C. M., Gómez, L. D., Gordon, D. R., Hobbs, R. J., Holt, A., Hopper, K. R., Hughes, C. E., LaHart, M., Leakey, R. R. B., Lee, W. G., Loope, L. L., Lorence, D. H., Louda, S. M., Lugo, A. E., McEvoy, P. B., Richardson, D. M., & Vitousek, P. M. (1999). Deliberate introductions of species: Research needs: benefits can be reaped, but risks are high, *BioScience*, 49(8), 619–630. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1313438>
- Fargione, J., Haase, D. L., Burney, O. T., Kildisheva, O. A., Edge, G., Cook-Patton, S. C., Chapman, T., Rempel, A., Hurteau, M. D., Davis, K. T., Dobrowski, S., Enebak, S., De La Torre, R., Bhuta, A. A. R., Cubbage, F., Kittler, B., Zhang, D., & Guldin, R. W. (2021). Challenges to the reforestation pipeline in the United States. *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*, 4, 629198. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2021.629198>
- Frazier, A. G., Johnson, M.-V. V. Fortini, L. B., Giardina, C. P., Grecni, Z. N., Kane, H. H., Keener, V. W., King, R., MacKenzie, R. A., Nobrega-Olivera, M., Oleson, K. L. L., Shuler, C. K., Singeo, A. K., Storlazzi, C. D., Wallsgrove, R. J., & Woodworth-Jefcoats, P. A. (2023). Ch. 30. Hawai'i and US-Affiliated Pacific Islands. In Crimmins, A. R., Avery, C. W., Easterling, D. R., Kunkel, K. E., Stewart, B. C., & Maycock, T. K. (Eds.) Fifth National Climate Assessment. U.S. Global Change Research Program, Washington, DC. <https://nca2023.globalchange.gov/chapter/30/>
- Great Lakes St. Lawrence Governors & Premiers. (2019). Governors and Premiers Support Law Enforcement Efforts to Hold Invasive Species Offenders Accountable. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://gsgp.org/projects/aquatic-invasive-species/ais-news/governors-and-premiers-support-law-enforcement-efforts-to-hold-invasive-species-offenders-accountable/>
- Haines, A. M., Costante, D., Freed, C., Achayaraj, G., Bleyer, L., Emeric, C., Smith, J. T., Nguyen, P. L., Patel, S. R., & Leu, M. (2024). The impact of invasive alien species on threatened and endangered species: A geographic perspective. *Wildlife Society Bulletin*, e1552. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wsb.1552>
- Hammond, A. (2021). Territorial exceptionalism and the American welfare state. *Michigan Law Review*, 119, 1639. <https://doi.org/10.36644/mlr.119.8.territorial>
- Hawaii Ant Group. (2007). A Plan for Prevention of Establishment of New Ant Species in Hawaii, with Special Attention to the Red Imported Fire Ant (*Solenopsis invicta*) and the Little Fire Ant (*Wasmannia auropunctata*). Accessed 18 November 2024. https://littlefireants.com/wp-content/uploads/Hawaii-Ant-Group-2007_compressed.pdf
- Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services [IPBES]. (2023). Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Roy, H. E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P., & Renard Truong, T. (Eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430682>

- International Maritime Organization. (2024a). Ballast Water Management. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.imo.org/en/ourwork/environment/pages/ballastwatermanagement.aspx>
- International Maritime Organization. (2024b). Biofouling. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.imo.org/en/OurWork/Environment/Pages/Biofouling.aspx>
- Invasive Species Advisory Committee [ISAC]. (2015). Enhancing the Effectiveness of Biological Control Programs of Invasive Species by Utilizing an Integrated Pest Management Approach. U.S. Department of the Interior, Washington, DC. https://www.doi.gov/sites/doi.gov/files/uploads/isac_biocontrols_white_paper_rev.pdf
- Invasive Species Advisory Committee [ISAC]. (2016). Addressing the Needs of Classical Biological Control Programs. U.S. Department of the Interior, Washington, DC. https://www.doi.gov/sites/doi.gov/files/uploads/isac_biocontrols2016_white_paper_rev.pdf
- Invasive Species Advisory Committee [ISAC]. (2023a). Invasive Species Threaten the Success of Climate Change Adaptation Efforts. U.S. Department of the Interior, Washington, DC. <https://www.doi.gov/sites/default/files/documents/2024-02/isac-climate-change-white-paper-november-2023.pdf>
- Invasive Species Advisory Committee [ISAC]. (2023b). Underserved Communities and Invasive Species. U.S. Department of the Interior, Washington, DC. <https://www.doi.gov/sites/default/files/documents/2024-02/isac-underserved-communities-white-paper-november-2023.pdf>
- Jewell, S. D. (2020). A century of injurious wildlife listing under the Lacey Act: A history. *Management of Biological Invasions*, 11(3), 356–371. <https://doi.org/10.3391/mbi.2020.11.3.01>
- Kappes, P. J., Benkwitt, C. E., Spatz, D. R., Wolf, C. A., Will, D. J., & Holmes, N. D. (2021). Do invasive mammal eradications from islands support climate change adaptation and mitigation? *Climate*, 9(12), 172. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli9120172>
- Kaufman, L. V., Yalamar, J., & Wright, M. G. (2020). Classical biological control of the erythrina gall wasp, *Quadrastichus erythrinae*, in Hawaii: Conserving an endangered habitat. *Biological Control*, 142, 104161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocontrol.2019.104161>
- Lenzner, B., Latombe, G., Capinha, C., Bellard, C., Courchamp, F., Diagne, C., Dullinger, S., Golivets, M., Irl, S. D. H., Kühn, I., Leung, B., Liu, C., Moser, D., Roura-Pascual, N., Seebens, H., Turbelin, A., Weigelt, P., & Essl, F. (2020). What will the future bring for biological invasions on islands? An expert-based assessment. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2020.00280>
- Luna-Mendoza, L., Aguirre-Muñoz, A., Hernández-Montoya, J. C., Torres-Aguilar, M., García-Carreón, J. S., Hernandez, O. P., Luvianos-Colin, S., Cárdenas, A. G., & Méndez Sánchez, F. A. (2019). Ten years after feral goat eradication: The active restoration of plant communities on Guadalupe Island, Mexico. In: Veitch, C.R., Clout, M.N., Martin, A.R., Russell, J.C., & West, C.J. (Eds.) *Island invasives: Scaling up to Meet the Challenge*, pp. 571–575. Occasional Paper SSC no. 62. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN. https://www.islas.org.mx/articulos_files/Luna-Mendoza%202019.pdf
- Lynch, A. J., Thompson, L. M., Morton, J. M., Beever, E. A., Clifford, M., Limpinsel, D., Magill, R. T., Magness, D. R., Melvin, T. A., Newman, R. A., Porath, M. T., Rahel, F. J., Reynolds, J. H., Schuurman, G. W., Sethi, S. A., & Wilkening, J. L. (2021). RAD adaptive management for transforming ecosystems. *BioScience*, 72(1), 45–56. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biab091>
- Mackenzie, J. S., & Jeggo, M. (2019). The one health approach—Why is it so important? *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 4(2), 88. <https://doi.org/10.3390/tropicalmed4020088>
- Maurer, A., & Hogue, R. H. (2020). Introduction: Transnational nuclear imperialisms. *Journal of Transnational American Studies*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.5070/T8112050495>
- Meissner, H. E., Bertone, C., Ferguson, L., Lemay, A., Newton, L., & Schwartzburg, K. (2009). Caribbean Pathway Analysis: A collaboration between the Caribbean Invasive Species Working Group and the U.S. Department of Agriculture: Evaluation of Pathways for Exotic Plant Pest Movement into and within the Greater Caribbean Region. United States Department of Agriculture, Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service, Plant Protection and Quarantine, Plant Epidemiology and Risk Analysis Laboratory, Raleigh, NC. <https://doi.org/10.22004/ag.econ.256352>
- Méndez-Lazaro, P. A., Chardón-Maldonado, P., Carrubba, L., Álvarez-Berrios, L., Barreto, M., Bowden, J. H., Crespo-Acevedo, W. I., Diaz, E. L., Gardner, L.S., Gonzalez, G., Guannel, G., Guido, Z., Harmsen, E. W., Leinberger, A. J., McGinley, K., Méndez-Lazaro, P. A., Ortiz, A. P., Pulwarty, R. S., Ragster, L. E., Rivera-Collazo, I. C., Santiago, R., Santos-Burgoa, C., & Vila-Biaggi, I. M. (2023). Ch. 23. US Caribbean. In Crimmins, A. R., Avery, C. W., Easterling, D. R., Kunkel, K. E., Stewart, B. C., & Maycock, T. K. (Eds.) *Fifth National Climate Assessment*. U.S. Global Change Research Program, Washington, DC. <https://doi.org/10.7930/NCA5.2023.CH23>
- Micronesia Islands Forum [MIF]. (2023). 25th MIF Communique. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.mifsecretariat.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/25th-MIF-Communique.pdf>
- Micronesia Islands Forum [MIF]. (2024a). 26th MIF Joint Communique. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://www.mifsecretariat.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/26th-MIF-Joint-Communique.pdf>

- Micronesian Island Forum [MIF]. (2024b). Letter to U.S. President Joseph R. Biden. June 5, 2024. Accessed 20 November 2024. <https://pohnpeistate.gov/fm/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/MIF-Letter-to-President-Biden.pdf>
- Moody, K. N., Scherer, A. E., O'Connor, D. A. J., Heim-Ballew, H., Lisi, P. J., Hogan D., McIntyre, P. B., & Blum, M. J. (2021). Effectiveness and outcomes of invasive species removal in Hawaiian streams. *Biological Invasions*, 23, 1739–1763. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-021-02468-w>
- Nagel, L. M., Palik, B. J., Battaglia, M. A., D'Amato, A. W., Guldin, J. M., Swanston, C. W., Janowiak, M. K., Powers, M. P., Joyce, L. A., Millar, C. I., Peterson, D. L., Ganio, L. M., Kirschbaum, C., & Roske, M. R. (2017). Adaptive silviculture for climate change: A national experiment in manager-scientist partnerships to apply an adaptation framework. *Journal of Forestry*, 115(3), 167–178. <https://doi.org/10.5849/jof.16-039>
- National Invasive Species Council [NISC]. (2024). How to Reduce the Risks of Introducing and Spreading Invasive Species in a Major Disaster. National Invasive Species Council. Washington, DC. <https://www.doi.gov/invasive-species-and-disasters>
- Paudel, S., Mansfield, S., Villamizar, L. F., Jackson, T. A., & Marshall, S. D. (2021). Can biological control overcome the threat from newly invasive coconut rhinoceros beetle populations (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae)? A review. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*, 114(2), 247–256. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aesa/saaa057>
- Pacific Ecological Security Conference [PESC]. (2022a). Pacific Biocontrol Strategic Action Plan. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7683179>
- Pacific Ecological Security Conference [PESC]. (2022b). Strategic Action Plan for Coconut Rhinoceros Beetle. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7683205>
- Pacific Ecological Security Conference [PESC]. (2022c). Biosecurity Plan for Invasive Ants in the Pacific. Accessed 18 November 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7683198>
- Reaser, J. K., Meyerson, L. A., Cronk, Q., De Poorter, M., Eldrege, L. G., Green, E., Kairo, M., Latasi, P., Mack, R. N., Mauremootoo, J., O'Dowd, D., Orapa, W., Sastroutomo, S., Saunders, A., Shine, C., Thrainsson, S., & Vaiutu, L. (2007). Ecological and socioeconomic impacts of invasive alien species in island ecosystems. *Environmental Conservation*, 34(2), 98–111. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892907003815>
- Rhyne, A. L., Tlustý, M. F., Szczebak, J. T., & Holmberg, R. J. (2017). Expanding our understanding of the trade in marine aquarium animals. *PeerJ*, 5, e2949. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.2949>
- Rosenau, N.A., Gignoux-Wolfsohn, S., Everett, R.A., Miller, A.W., Minton, M.S., & Ruiz. G.M. (2021). Considering commercial vessels as potential vectors of stony coral tissue loss disease. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 709764. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.709764>
- Ruiz-Allais, J. P., Amaro, M. E., McFadden, C. S., Halász, A., & Benayahu, Y. (2014). The first incidence of an alien soft coral of the family Xeniidae in the Caribbean, an invasion in eastern Venezuelan coral communities. *Coral Reefs* 33, 287. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00338-013-1122-1>
- Ruiz-Allais, J. P., Benayahu, Y., & Lasso-Alcalá O. M. (2021). The invasive octocoral *Unomia stolonifera* (Alcyonacea, Xeniidae) is dominating the benthos in the Southeastern Caribbean Sea. Accessed 19 November 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4784708>
- S.140-115th Congress (2018). Frank LoBiondo Coast Guard Authorization Act of 2018. Congress.gov, Library of Congress. Accessed 19 November 2024. <https://www.congress.gov/115/bills/s140/BILLS-115s140enr.pdf>
- Sardain, A., Sardain, E., & Leung, B. (2019). Global forecasts of shipping traffic and biological invasions to 2050. *Nature Sustainability*, 2, 274–282. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0245-y>
- Schoonover, R., Cavallo, C., & Caltabiano, I. (2021). The Security Threat That Binds Us: The Unraveling of Ecological and Natural Security and What the United States Can Do About It. Femia, F., & Rezzonico, A. (Eds.). *The Converging Risks Lab, an institute of The Council on Strategic Risks*. Washington, DC. https://councilonstrategicrisks.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/The-Security-Threat-That-Binds-Us_2021_2-1.pdf
- Seebens, H., Blackburn, T. M., Dyer, E. E., Genovesi, P., Hulme, P. E., Jeschke, J. M., Pagad, S., Pyšek, P., van Kleunen, M., Winter, M., Ansong, M., Arianoutsou, M., Bacher, S., Blasius, B., Brockhoff, E. G., Brundu, G., Capinha, C., Causton, C. E., Celesti-Grapow, L., Dawson, W., Dullinger, S., Economo, E. P., Fuentes, N., Guénard, B., Jäger, H., Kartesz, J., Kenis, M., Kühn, I., Lenzner, B., Liebhold, A., Mosen, A., Moser, D., Nentwig, W., Nishino, M., Pearman, D., Pergl, J., Rabitsch, W., Rojas-Sandoval, J., Roques, A., Rorke, S., Rossinelli, S., Roy, H. E., Scalera, R., Schindler, S., Štajerová, K., Tokarska-Guzik, Walker, K., Ward, D. F., Yamanaka, T., & Essl, F. (2018). Global rise in emerging alien species results from increased accessibility of new source pools. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(10), E2264–E2273. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1719429115>
- Sheppard, A. W., Paynter, Q., Mason, P., Murphy, S., Stoett, P., Cowan, P., Brodeur, J., Warner, K., Villegas, C., Shaw, R., Hinz, H., Hill, M., & Genovesi, P. (2020). IUCN SSC Invasive Species Specialist Group. *The Application of Classical Biological Control for the Management of Established Invasive Alien Species Causing Environmental Impacts*. The Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity Technical Series No. 91. Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity, Montreal, Canada. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/publications/cbd-ts-91-en.pdf>

- Simpson, A., & Eyler, M.C. (2018). First Comprehensive List of Non-Native Species Established in Three Major Regions of the United States: U.S. Geological Survey Open-File Report 2018-1156. U.S. Geological Survey, Reston, VA. <https://doi.org/10.3133/ofr20181156>
- Skrivanek, A., & Wusinich-Mendez, D. (2020). NOAA Strategy for Stony Coral Tissue Loss Disease Response and Prevention. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Silver Spring, MD Accessed 19 November 2024. https://coast.noaa.gov/data/coralreef_noaa_gov/media/docs/NOAA_SCTLD_Strategy_2020.pdf
- State of Hawai'i Department of Business, Economic Development, & Tourism. (2022). 2022 Annual Visitor Research Report. Accessed 19 November 2024. <https://files.hawaii.gov/dbedt/visitor/visitor-research/2022-annual-visitor.pdf>
- Studivan, M. S., Baptist, M., Molina, V., Riley, S., First, M., Soderberg, N., Rubin, E., Rossin, A., Holstein, D. M., & Enochs, I. C. (2022). Transmission of stony coral tissue loss disease (SCTLD) in simulated ballast water confirms the potential for ship-born spread. *Scientific Reports*, 12, 19248. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-21868-z>
- Swaminathan, S. D., Lafferty, K. D. Knight, N. S., & Altieri, A. H. (2024). Stony coral tissue loss disease indirectly alters reef communities. *Science Advances*, 10(18), eadk6808. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adk6808>
- Toledo-Rodriguez, D. A., Veglia, A., Jimenez Marrero, N. M., Gomez-Samot, J. M., McFadden, C. S., Weil, E., & Schizas, N. V. (2024). Shadows over Caribbean reefs: Identification of a new invasive soft coral species, *Xenia umbellata*, in southwest Puerto Rico. *bioRxiv: the preprint server for biology*, 2024.05.07.592775. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.05.07.592775>
- Trauernicht, C., Ticktin, T., Fraioli, H., Hastings, Z., & Tsuneyoshi, A. (2018). Active restoration enhances recovery of a Hawaiian mesic forest after fire. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 411, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2018.01.005>
- Turbelin, A. J., Cuthbert, R. N., Essl, F., Haubrock, P. J., Ricciardi, A., & Courchamp, F. (2023). Biological invasions are as costly as natural hazards. *Perspectives in Ecology and Conservation*, 21(2), 143–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecon.2023.03.002>
- Turner, B. C. (2024). European Green Crab 2025-2031 Management Plan for Washington. Washington Department of Fish and Wildlife, Olympia, WA. <https://wdfw.wa.gov/publications/02537>
- United Nations General Assembly. (1982). United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea. <https://www.refworld.org/legal/agreements/unga/1982/en/40182>
- U.S. Department of Agriculture [USDA]. (2024a). Fruit Fly Exclusion and Detection Program Strategy Fiscal Years 2024-2028. <https://www.aphis.usda.gov/sites/default/files/feed-strategy-plan.pdf>
- U.S. Department of Agriculture [USDA]. (2024b). Greater Caribbean Safeguarding Initiative. Accessed 19 November 2024. <https://www.aphis.usda.gov/aqi/gcsi>
- U.S. Department of Agriculture Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service [USDA APHIS]. (2019). Review of PERAL 2009 Greater Caribbean Pathway Analysis. <https://www.aphis.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2019-review-of-peral-2009-gcr-pathway-analysis.pdf>
- U.S. Department of the Interior [DOI]. (2016). Safeguarding America's Lands and Waters from Invasive Species: A National Framework for Early Detection and Rapid Response. <https://www.doi.gov/sites/doi.gov/files/National%20EDRR%20Framework.pdf>
- U.S. Department of the Navy. (2015). Regional Biosecurity Plan for Micronesia and Hawaii: Volume I. University of Guam and the Secretariat of the Pacific Community (Eds.). https://www.doi.gov/sites/doi.gov/files/uploads/pac_regional_biosecurity_plan_for_micronesia_and_hawaii_volume_i.pdf
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service [USFWS]. (2024a). Environmental Conservation Online System. Accessed 19 November 2024. <https://ecos.fws.gov/ecp/>
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service [USFWS]. (2024b). Memorandum of Understanding between U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and Island Conservation. https://www.fws.gov/sites/default/files/documents/2024-09/usfws_island-restoration-2015-mou-and-8-addendums_092624.pdf
- U.S. Government Accountability Office. (2024). Federal Workforce: Actions Needed to Improve Recruitment and Retention in Alaska, Hawaii, and U.S. Territories. <https://www.gao.gov/assets/gao/25-106527.pdf>
- USVI Bureau of Economic Research. (2024). Economic Report. Accessed 19 November 2024. <https://usviber.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Tourism-indicator-2022-12-28-23-1.pdf>
- Vitousek, P. M., D'Antonio, C. M., Loope, L. L., Rejmánek, M., & Westbrooks, R. (1997). Introduced species: A significant component of human-caused global change. *New Zealand Journal of Ecology*, 21(1), 1–16. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24054520>
- Watson, G. J., Kohler, S., Collins, J. J., Richir, J., Arduini, D., Calabrese, C., & Schaefer, M. (2023). Can the global marine aquarium trade (MAT) be a model for sustainable coral reef fisheries? *Science Advances*, 9(49), eadh4942. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adh4942>
- Weidlich, E. W., Flórido, F. G., Sorrini, T. B., & Brancalion, P. H. (2020). Controlling invasive plant species in ecological restoration: A global review. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 57, 1806–1817. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13656>
- Zahawi, R. A., Reid, J. L., & Holl, K. D. (2014). Hidden costs of passive restoration. *Restoration Ecology*, 22, 284–287. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rec.12098>